

Unmasking marriage fraud: Closing the gap between love and criminal motives.

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Abstract: Criminals marry someone to use them as a "cell". The spouse can be a criminal without the other spouse knowing it. Mainly spouses stay together because they cannot believe the crimes happened. The reasons for marriage might not be honest, it is not out of true love, it could be out of a criminal motive, which would be marriage fraud. Such marriage fraud can be groomed by organized crime. There is a research gap between the benefits of cohabitation and marriage and actually not true love and thus fraud in the relationship or marriage. The gap between the benefits of marriage, and actual, when contact, relationships, and marriages are fraud and forced marriage, as it is not true love, it is pressured, or set up, needs to be closed. So, people live free and safe lives, making only their own choices, without any influence. It can be organized by criminals, locals, family members, corrupt people in jobs, courts, and government, and Transnational Crime Organizations. It can also be a part of war motives, terrorism, or mafias. It can also be a part of religion, and people wanting to influence others. This can be with motives about wanting to influence their beliefs, and lifestyles, education, jobs, or any other possible influence and changes they want to see. It can also be to have some slavery, for example, someone hating colored, marrying one to have a slave at home. We need to every detail research on it, and also on friending, neighbors, and all other social activities and forces. Crime groups use streets, towns, and regions, also countries, and are transnational. Also, it should include, how crime groups start to live around to control relationships and targets. Also, it needs to be about espionage and wars, and war crimes, to complete the knowledge.

Keywords: forensic psychology, marriage, criminal, marriage fraud, organized crime.

Essence

In essence, this article is a call for research and awareness about the potential misuse of personal relationships in criminal activities and the broader societal implications of these practices. The essence of the article is also about the role and potential misuse of personal relationships, such as marriage, and the possibility of marriages being used as a cover for illicit activities, and organized crime, with one spouse potentially being unaware of the other's criminal endeavors. These relationships may not be based on love, but rather on ulterior motives related to crime. The article is also about the need for comprehensive research into this area, stating that there is a significant gap in our understanding of how these relationships may be used in the context of crime, corruption, and coercion. This could involve a variety of actors, from local criminals and family members to transnational crime organizations, and could be related to a range of issues, including war, terrorism, religious influence, and racism. It also can extend beyond marriage to other forms of social interactions, such as friendships and neighborhood relations. These relationships too could be influenced by criminal elements, potentially at different levels of society and across different countries and regions. Future research should also include espionage, wars, and war crimes, and research how these elements are interlinked.

Introduction

Criminals marry someone to use them as a "cell". The spouse can be a criminal without the other spouse knowing it. Mainly spouses stay together because they cannot believe the crimes happened (Huels, N.D.). When convicted divorce rate is only 32% (Ramos, 2019). A spouse can also be used to hide crimes or can be forced to marry. The reasons are not honest, it is not out of true love, it is out of a criminal motive, which would be marriage fraud (Parkinson, N.D.), such marriage fraud can be groomed by organized crime (Cascio, 2017;

Metropolitan Police, N.D.; Taher, 2011). Married couples can be criminals together, like the robbery team Barrow and Parker, named Bonnie and Clyde, in the 1930s. They robbed banks together and committed crimes, also murder, in a spree of 21 months (Jenkins, and Philip, 2023). John Dillinger was also alike Bonnie and Clyde, a crime team with his spouse, Beryl Hovious in the 1930s. But they divorced, and he remarried and became a new team with his new spouse Evelyn Frechette (Murderpedia, N.D.). This research article is made to review the literature and find the gaps in the literature to create ideas for future research to close the gaps.

Benefits of marriage

Employment, marriage, and parenting can lead to reinforcing social ties and withholding from crime (Corman et al, 2011; Sampson, et al, 2006). Also, cohabiting can lower crime, especially among women. But marriage has a bigger effect (Gottlieb, and Sugie, 2019). Especially in males marriage has an effect in lowering criminal behavior. For females, it would then, in marriage, not make a difference (Zoutewelle-Terovan, 2014). Even teens thinking of marriage within 5 years lead to fewer crimes (Finney, 2016). Life events like marriage do not always bring a positive effect. Also, life events can cause criminal behavior in parents, or adults. For example, if fathers have a newborn born with a very severe disease within three years fathers are more likely than without this event to engage in a crime in which they get convicted. Also, the factors of work and parental relationships are variables in that (Corman et al, 2011). Life events can trigger crime, but seeing a violent crime, would be the biggest trigger, especially within a week after seeing violent crime someone with schizophrenia would commit more likely crimes, then, after this also someone with bipolar disorder, and after these two also people with no psychiatric diagnosis. So, seeing violent crime causes a lot of crime in people with or without disorders (Beall, 2016). Still, there is a research gap between the benefits of cohabitation and marriage and actually not true love and

thus fraud in the relationship or marriage. People then live with others who actually use them, especially criminals and dark triad criminals can set up contact, groom, and forced marriages, in ways that are very detailed, or deep, and without the spouse, boyfriend, girlfriend, or contacts knowing it. Also, it can come from local or religious, or government or crime group forces, that actually enforce in a system a lifestyle, which pressures to marry a "same kind of person", or puts people together, which is a form of slavery as well, and leads to contacts one else would not have. This can shape the future of people, and people need to be free from influences, and forces. People can be misformed by such forced living.

Research gaps in forced contact and relationships

The gap between the benefits of marriage, and actual, when contact, relationships, and marriages are fraud and forced marriage, as it is not true love, it is pressured, or set up, needs to be closed. So, people live free and safe lives, making only their own choices, without any influence. It can be organized by criminals, locals, family members, corrupt people in jobs, courts, and government, and Transnational Crime Organizations. It can also be a part of war motives, terrorism, or mafias. It can also be a part of religion, and people wanting to influence others. This can be with motives about wanting to influence their beliefs, and lifestyles, education, jobs, or any other possible influence and changes they want to see. It can also be to have some slavery, for example, someone hating colored, marrying one to have a slave at home. We need to every detail research on it, and also on friending, neighbors, and all other social activities and forces. Crime groups use streets, towns, and regions, also countries, and are transnational. They also do "home milking", illegal renting, exploiting renters, and human traffic, and have drug labs, etc. All kinds of crimes are related to this. We need to find any detail related to forced contact, and marriages, and clean the streets, and towns from crime. Also, internationally. People around the families, and children, plan, and

target, while it has to be a free-living and from real love, not from any frauds. Even blind dates by friends could be seen as forced marriage, as it can be forced to start a relationship, while the entire family, or group already has planned it.

Transnational Crime Organizations (TCO)

Crime groups can groom, and play a big role in forced marriages, human trafficking, sexual exploitation, forced labor, and financial gain. They can groom children and families from the start of life, and try to live around with groups, to stalk, hack, track, mob, doxx, and have actually cyberwar, drug war, IS war, nazi reliving and terrorism, other religious wars, and cults, and for example, old Sovjet war ideas, or reliving it, and KGB and army from the wartime going into the mafia and other crime groups, because they lost the "work" from the wars. This is for all criminal groups also how they can go down into mafia, drug war, or religious wars. Also, there are current wars they could feel connected to and work for, in combination with different crime groups (Europol, N.D.; Obama White House, N.D.; Singh, 2021; Slade, 2019). These can be articles we need a lot of research on, to close the gaps, and get them in vision to track who from the transnational crime organizations are corrupt locally and in other countries, and actually have such history of crime and also actually have marriage fraud and forced contacts, grooming people and using corruption to influence and how they get into society, with actually other plans. Not sincere contacts, and marriages can be very good topics for articles leading to a better cleaning up of crime in the countries at work, in the streets, and in society and understanding what is behind these crimes, and recognizing these ways they work. Also, it can show their routes, and targets, how long they target to groom and how much they mob, and stalk, and what other crimes they do to get to their targets, like start living around and next doors, and creating drugs labs and use old Sovjet chemicals and other tactics from war crimes done they ll now use onto civilians. They might also as crime groups work more together in the streets, and having together drugs labs,

and other crimes, create an "around" children and families, and are corrupt with locals, for example, pedophiles. Using courts and systems to make it sound, but actually, they do a lot of crimes next door to them, or in society. Where also these labs and grooming lead to rapes, tracking, spy cams, break-ins, and all kind of crimes, but also deaths. Where they are on the one hand criminals in the homes, and around, grooming, and on the other corrupt with locals in courts, social work, youth care, and other jobs, and another hand even call with transnational crime organizations leaders, and with war motives, or even more direct with orders to control targets and worse. With this comes along, forced contacts, set-up contacts, and harass, and creating traps and set-ups, including marriages, and relationships the way they want it. Including stalking wherever the victims go, which can be entire streets and towns they target and follow, to create drugs towns, or try to even create drug states, and other types of crimes, to set up different religions against each other and other types of differences that create a war situation, eventually, which they will use again, as planned. We will need to close those gaps and research more on how they connect and expand in countries, and on their routes. Also, how espionage is the number one crime and should be punished, and include how they influence and do all other crimes. Which starts with espionage. From there, they can build out. They come to see what others do and work with that information, which they also sell or spread, to other criminals. This can keep victims trapped in ways we need to know and solve and we will need any detail on, so we can take it out. So, people will be free again and marry without these influences.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the phenomenon of criminals marrying individuals for criminal purposes, often without the knowledge of their spouses, raises important concerns about marriage fraud and criminal ideas about targeted people. The existence of this research gap

regarding the benefits of marriage versus the prevalence of fraud and forced marriages highlights the need for further investigation and action. It is essential to close this gap to ensure that individuals can live free and safe lives, making their own choices without any external influence. Addressing this issue requires collaboration and cooperation among law enforcement agencies, policymakers, and researchers to develop effective strategies to identify and prevent these fraudulent marriages. By doing so, we can strive towards creating a society where genuine love and trust prevail, and individuals can enter into marriages based on true affection and mutual respect. In future research, one could include methods, to track the types of crimes behind the marriages, but also expand this research to simply contacts, and other relationships, like street connections, neighbors, and family connections. Which become an influence in relationships and marriages. Freeing people from local, or other influences. People can realize with this research what true love means, and what other motives might be. They can get aware of the crime scenes that might target them and solve the crime in the jobs, the courts, the crime scenes, the streets, and governments, and solve this corrupt connection.

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